

STRATEGY TO ENHANCE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

S.L. Bai*, H.C. Guo, Y.J. Ren, M. Maqbool, H. Y. Niu,
R.C. Lv, L. C. Ren

School of Materials Science and Engineering
Peking University, China.

1. Modified graphene/PA6 nanocomposites

Principle of graphene modification

Distribution of graphene sheets

Thermal conductivity VS of graphene loading

2. Graphene/carbon fiber/PVDF nanocomposites

The nano-urethane linkage-based modified graphene and carbon fibers is fabricated through the process. Interestingly, the prepared composite with PVDF matrix shows an unprecedented TC of $7.96\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ at a low loading of 13.8 wt%.

Schematic for the fabrication of NUL-Gr/CFs and NUL-Gr/CFs/PVDF composite

3. FDM 3D printing of graphene/TPU composites

The alignment of graphene induced by shear and friction force during FDM 3D printing is achieved in TPU composites.

TC[⊥] of TP1 and TP2

(a) Battery test setup. (b) IR images of pure TPU pack (left) and Gr/TPU pack (right). (c) temperature

Thank you!

Prof. & Dr. Shu-Lin Bai
School of Materials Science and Engineering
Peking University, 100871 Beijing, China
Email: slbai@pku.edu.cn